

Protein based biocomposites from cottonseed meals reinforced with chitin nanoparticles

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Acknowledgements

- Cotton Inc. (Project number 23-886)

Demand for bio-based materials

- Petro-based materials
 - Non-renewable
 - Environmental persistence
- Natural biodegradable polymers
 - Natural polysaccharides
 - Natural proteins

Cottonseed Protein as matrix

- **Cost-effective**
price 20%-50% lower than soybean meals
- **Protein-rich**
Containing 40% proteins
- **Containing gossypol**
Not suitable to serve as food or feed
Natural antimicrobial agent
- **Suitable protein structure for spinning**
High molecular weight
High degree of disulfide crosslinkages
- **Value Addition to cotton industry**
Producing 1 kg of cottonseed protein fibers could add \$6 values

Previous efforts and challenges

Extraction and dissolution process

- Damage to protein backbones
 - High alkalinity
- Failure to break all intra- and inter-molecular interactions
 - Disulfide bonds, hydrophobic interactions

Film development

- Insufficient extension of protein molecules
- Poor recovery of disulfide cross-linkages

Low extraction yield (24-67%)

Low mechanical properties:
brittleness, poor wet stability

Reinforcement

- Problems
 - Poor interfacial bonding
 - Brittleness
- Partially deacetylated chitin nanoparticles
 - Free amine groups
 - Interaction

Cost-effective extraction of cottonseed proteins

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Partially deacetylated chitin nanoparticles

Characterization of chitin nanoparticles

Degrees of deacetylation

$$DD (\%) = \left(1 - \frac{\frac{I_{Ac}}{3}}{\frac{I_{H2-6}}{6}} \right) * 100$$

Where I_{Ac} is the integral intensity of acetyl group and I_{H2-6} is the summation integral intensities of H2, H3, H1, H5, H6.

Mechanical properties of biocomposites

Summary

- Ductile and wet-durable protein biocomposites from cottonseed meals reinforced by chitin-nanoparticles with controlled deacetylation have been developed.
- The resulting biocomposites demonstrated exceptional mechanical properties and moisture stability.
- A sustainable and high-performance solution for applications requiring ductility, toughness, and moisture resistance.